

A STUDY ON DESIGN AND EMOTION BOOKS FROM THE 1980s TO 2011

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, there has been a growing interest in using emotional factors in product design in order to improve the interaction between humans and objects or interfaces. Therefore, this article presents a study on the editorial publications in book form from 1980s to 2011 that are related to Design and emotions. First, we present emotion in its various concepts to understand the relationship of meaning with the knowledge area of Design. After, we present the methodology used to conduct this research. And from the data collection the analysis of 49 books found is performed by considering three areas: publications, authorship and content. The results of this study indicate the evolution of the field theory and may assist those who want to include emotional factors in the design of products, digital interfaces, services, brands to improve interaction with their users.

Keywords: Design, emotion, human factors, interaction, books

INTRODUCTION

The necessity of sensitizing designers that products can produce unexpected or unwanted effects in users has been increased the number of works published in recent decades in the Design and Emotion field studies (Desmet and Hekkert 2009). The importance and the seduction that products have on people's life also have been factors of interest of researchers on the area (Norman 2005).

As the Design and Emotion is a theoretical field in expansion, a large number of publications in form of

books, journal articles, dissertations and thesis have been published with this subject recently.

In this rich scenario, this research stemmed from the need for the researcher, who had little expertise in Design and Emotion area, knowing which are the most important books and authors that should be studied to integrate emotional factors in product development.

The first results showed that the field of Design and Emotion has a great potential as an object of study with respect to its publications. And the growing number of publications could be indicative of the theoretical evolution of the field.

Therefore, the article aims to present a study in Design and Emotion through an analysis of publications in book form from 1980 until 2011 (August). The choice of books as object of research is due to the nature of consolidation that knowledge acquires when published in this format.

The delimitation of the period was due to investigate the possibility of expanding the research on Design and Emotion in recent decades, which can be verified by the publication of books. This could be a clue to understand the evolution and the consolidation of this theory field since a book is a form of dissemination of knowledge not only for the scientific public but also for society.

The results of this study serve to assist those who want to include emotional factors in the design of industrial products, digital interfaces, services, brands, etc. and to improve interaction with their users, enriching their experience. For those who are beginners in the area, this article presents a list of all

books found from the 1980s to 2011 (August) and some references from other areas of knowledge related to Design, and for the most experienced, presents data for further analysis on the subject.

In this paper, first, we will describe the concept of *emotion*, which over time, has changed their meaning. After, the methodology used to conduct this research will be presented. The analysis from the data collected was divided into three main areas:

- Publications.
- Authorship.
- Content.

It is hoped that this study contributes to highlight the importance of the use of emotional aspects in the development of product, interfaces, services etc. and encourage the reflection in order to attend emotional needs, improving the user experience.

EMOTION

To comprehend the Design researches related to emotional factors, it is necessary to know the meaning and origin of the word *emotion*. According to the dictionary Michaelis (2011), it is possible to define it in three ways:

- **Psychic:** the act of moving.
- **Psychological:** involves complex moral state that changes in respiration, circulation and secretions, as well as implications for mental excitement or depression, the intense emotions intellectual functions deplete or disrupt.
- **Physical:** excitement, shock (physical or moral sense).

To understand the diversity of its meanings, it is necessary to resort to Etymology. According to the Mirador International Encyclopedia (1999), the word *emotion* came from Latin *emovere* understood as to scroll, to move and to shake.

Émouvoir, the French word which originated emotion, also referred to movement and physical agitation, and

the English word originally meant movement, civil unrest, riot and disorder (Mirador International Encyclopedia 1999).

The understanding as a strong feeling occurs in 1650, and it's only around 1808 that start the use of the definition that is adopted today, which would in any feeling, characterized by agitation of body and mind (Mirador International Encyclopedia 1999, Harper 2010, Oxford 2011).

Even if the term *emotion* has only been introduced around 1570, researches about this subject are much older. The first known studies on the pleasure, for example, came from Greek philosophers. From 435 BC, the philosophers Aristippus and Epicurus spoke on this subject, which is considered as a hedonistic thought, a philosophical and moral doctrine based on pleasure as the supreme good of human life.

Over time, another works about emotions were written as *The Passions of the Soul (Les passion de l'ame)*, authored by the philosopher René Descartes in 1649, and *The Expression of Emotions in Man and Animals* by the British naturalist Charles Darwin in 1871. *The Passions of the Soul* was the last work of Descartes. This was written during the exchange of correspondence with Princess Elisabeth in winter 1645 to 1646 talking about the relationship between body and soul. Darwin's work describes how humans and animals express their emotions using the evolutionary theory.

The awareness of the importance of studies related to emotions occurs between 1990 and 2000 (Desmet and Hekkert 2009).

In 1995, psychologist and Doctor of Psychology, Daniel Goleman, launched *Emotional Intelligence* affirming that emotions play an important role in decision making and individual success. In the same year, the physician and neuroscientist António Damásio publishes *Descartes' Error - Emotion, Reason and the Human Brain*. The book makes a reference to the Cartesian idea that mental processes are separated from the body.

Focused on the economic issue, Joseph B. Pine and James H. Gilmore published the book *The Experience Economy in 1999*. With the fierce competition, companies need to differentiate themselves to keep and increase customers. The authors proposed the idea of not just selling products and services, but provide user experiences in order to stay close to them. This book has been updated and published again in 2011, after more than 10 years of its publishing.

The idea of *The Dream Society*, by Rolf Jensen, came from a question of one of his customers: "*What would come after the Information Society?*". It is because not only the price or convenience would be decisive factors when purchasing products. In *The Dream Society*, the value of the products depends on the story they could tell, the emotions that are involved to get them and to possess them.

Therefore, emotions have been the object of research over time in various areas of knowledge such as Philosophy, Biology, Psychology, Medicine, Economics and so on. This studies show the character not only multidisciplinary but also transdisciplinary of this research. Design will inevitably seek theoretical knowledge in other areas because its objective is to meet the needs of its users regarding functional, social and aesthetic aspects.

METHODOLOGY

The motivation of this research stemmed from the need to study the emotional factors that can be related to the Design. This was part of theoretical research done by the author to her Dissertation. For this reason, the first searches were more related to the subject at the level of curiosity without the rigor of systematization.

The search for the Design and Emotion theme was made in various types of publications:

- Scientific articles (printed and online).
- Dissertations (printed and online).
- Thesis (printed and online).
- Books (printed and online).

- Google website.
- Google Books website.
- Amazon website.
- Cultura website.
- Saraiva website.
- Research groups websites.
- Publishing Houses websites.
- Authors or editors' websites.
- Websites in general.

The research was done mainly through the internet that enables quick and easy access to publications. The keywords used in search engines were: *design emotion, emotion, emotional, design and emotion, emotional design, emotional design, affective*.

During the searches, the existence of Related Books section in websites as Amazon and Google Books allowed to extend the number of the publications found. The possibility of viewing fully or partially of most of these publications made possible to verify the adequacy of them to the research.

In addition, through books, journal articles, dissertations and thesis in physical and digital form, it was possible to find new authors and works related to the Design and Emotion using references.

The large volume of information found and the great potential to research this subject led to turn into a scientific research. It was necessary to add, manage and retrieve all links using a bookmark online service (Delicious) and organize all data into a spreadsheet using an editor (Microsoft Excel).

Since were found more information to each search, it was necessary to create more criteria and repeat it several times to complement the books already included. Also, there was an exhaustive repetition to confirm some data, because they often are showed conflicting, being necessary to consult other sources as publishers' website or even printed or online versions.

Delimit the research also was a challenge. The Design and Emotion field of study is broad, encompassing several disciplines such as *product experience, user experience, interaction, usability, ergonomics* etc. Not all the books consulted have the words in the title *Design, emotion* or *emotional*. However, the reason for using them is the approach of emotional factors in the development of products, services, interfaces etc.

To verify the adequacy of the books to the proposed research criteria, it was necessary to check partial or total availability in print or online versions. On websites like Google Books and Amazon, most of publications allow you to view the abstract, the table of contents and excerpts, which were devoted more attention during the search. The criteria and justifications for their use in the cataloging of books can be viewed in Table 1:

Criteria	Rationale
Publication year	Year of first publication
Title of book	Book title in original language or in English
Author(s) / editor(s)	Full names(s) of author(s) or editor(s)
Author(s) or editor(s) formal education	The knowledge of author(s) or editor(s) formal education allows to understand what are the views of the subject
Collection of articles	If the publication is a collection of articles: <i>Yes or No</i>
Proceedings	If the publication is the result of a scientific event: <i>Yes or No</i>
Internationally authorship	If the book is a collection of articles, if they are owned by authors from different countries: <i>Yes or No</i>
Translation into Portuguese	If there is translation for Portuguese: <i>Yes or No</i>
Brazilian author	If the publication is written by a Brazilian: <i>Yes or No</i>
Product, digital interface, brand, lighting and/or service	In which focus were devoted to the publication content. This information allows to know what are the applications of Design and Emotion.

Availability of the summary or chapters of the publication	The availability of the summary or book chapters allows verify the adequacy of the contents of the publication: <i>Yes or No</i>
Website	Electronic address

Table 1. Criteria used in the construction of the spreadsheet.

With the large volume of books found, these were listed in ascending order of year of publication and grouped by decades. This organization allowed an overview of the number of the books released in recent years.

As to the authorship, a point to note relates to the formal education of the author(s)/editor(s). It was important to understand the relationship of Design and Emotion publications with other areas of knowledge. The possibility of being a collection of articles would help to identify if they were originated from events, research groups or were written by only one author.

Regarding content, the spreadsheet started with just the possibility of the books were only focused on products and interfaces, however, research has revealed a larger field of application of Design and Emotion, which will be shown later in the analysis of the results. Furthermore, a lot of words was found in books relating Design to emotion, which ultimately increases the quantity of books and also hamper the delimitation of the field theory.

The following sections will present some research results from three perspectives: publications, authorship and content.

PUBLICATIONS

Altogether, there were found 49 books on Design and Emotion (Table 2):

Title of book	Author / Editor
Objects of Desire: Design and Society Since 1750	Adrian Forty
Manufactured pleasures: psychological responses to design	Ray Crozier
Affective Computing	Rosalind W. Picard

Human Factors in Product Design: Current Practice and Future Trends	William S. Green and Patrick W. Jordan (ed.)
The inmates are running the asylum	Alan Cooper
Hertzian Tales: Electronic Products, Aesthetic Experience, and Critical Design	Anthony Dunne
Designing Pleasurable Products	Patrick W. Jordan
Affective Interactions: Towards a New Generation of Computer Interfaces	Ana Paiva (ed.)
Emotional Branding: The New Paradigm for Connecting Brands to People	Marc Gobé
Pleasure with Products: Beyond Usability	William S. Green and Patrick W. Jordan (ed.)
Designing Emotions	Pieter M.A. Desmet
The Human-Computer Interaction Handbook: Fundamentals, Evolving Technologies and Emerging Applications	Andrew Sears e Julie A. Jacko (ed.)
Design and Emotion	Deana McDonagh, Paul Hekkert, Jeroen van Erp and Diane Gyi (ed.)
Funology: From Usability to Enjoyment (Human-Computer Interaction Series)	Mark A. Blythe, Kess Overbeeke, Andrew F. Monk and Peter C. Wright (ed.)
Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things	Donald Norman
Emotionally Durable Design: Objects, Experiences and Empathy	Jonathan Chapman
Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction: First International Conference, ACII 2005, Beijing, China, October 22-24, 2005	Jianhua Tao, Tieniu Tan and Rosalind W. Picard (ed.)
Brandjam: Humanizing Brands Through Emotional Design	Marc Gobé

The Power of Design: ostentation to emotion	Katia Faggiani
Aesthetic computing	Paul A. Fishwick (ed.)
Joël Desgrippes and Marc Gobé on the emotional brand experience	Joël Desgrippes and Marc Gobé
Ergonomics and Design, pleasure, comfort and risk in the use of products	Júlio Carlos de Souza van der Linden
Human-computer Interaction: HCI intelligent multimodal interaction environments	Julie A. Jacko (ed.)
Product Experience	Hendrik N. J. Schifferstein and Paul Hekkert (ed.)
Design & Emotion Moves	Pieter M.A. Desmet, Jeroen van Erp and Marianne Karlsson (ed.)
Emotional Bonding with Products: Investigating Product Attachment from a Design Perspective	Ruth Mugge
Affect and emotion in human-computer interaction: from theory to applications	Christian Peter e Russell Beale (ed.)
Design Ergonomics Emotion	Vera Damazio and Cláudia Mont'alvão (ed.)
Probing Experience: From Assessment of User Emotions and Behaviour to Development of Products (Philips Research Book Series)	Joyce Westerink, Martin Ouwerkerk, Therese J. M. Overbeek and W. Frank Pasveer (ed.)
Designing Emotions in Online Travel	Soraia Cardoso and René Vaartjes
Awareness Systems: Advances in Theory, Methodology and Design	Panos Markopoulos, Boris De Ruyter and Wendy Mackay (ed.)
Affective information processing	Jianhua Tao and Tieniu Tan (ed.)
Handling Emotions in Human-Computer Dialogues	Johannes Pittermann, Angela Pittermann and Wolfgang Minker

A Study on Variable Selection for Kansei Engineering System: Applications for Product Design	Chih-Chieh Yang
Built to Love: Creating Products That Captivate Customers	Peter Boatwright and Jonathan Cagan
Kansei Engineering and Soft Computing: Theory and Practice	Ying Dai, Basabi Chakraborty and Minghui Shi (ed.)
On the Way to Fun: An Emotion-Based Approach to Successful Game Design	Roberto Dillon
Stage Design Emotions	Ralph Larmann
Kansei Engineering: Kansei/Affective Engineering (Industrial Innovation)	Mitsuo Nagamachi (ed.)
Mitsuo Nagamachi (ed.)	Mitsuo Nagamachi and Anitawati Mohd Lokman
Emotional Engineering: Service Development	Shuichi Fukuda (ed.)
Light and Emotions: Exploring Lighting Cultures. Conversations with Lighting Designers	Vincent Laganier and Jasmine van der Pol (ed.)
Sensing Emotions: The impact of context on experience measurements (Philips Research Book Series)	Joyce Westerink, Martijn Krans and Martin Ouwkerk (ed.)
Emotion@Web: Emotionale Websites durch Bewegtbild und Sound-Design	Pierre Hansch and Christian Rentschler
New Perspectives on Affect and Learning Technologies (Explorations in the Learning Sciences, Instructional Systems and Performance Technologies)	Rafael A. Calvo and Sidney K. D'Mello (ed.)
Shoes, cars, and other love stories: Investigating the experience of love for products	Beatriz Russo
Designing for Emotion	Aaron Walter
Seductive Interaction Design: Creating Playful, Fun, and Effective User Experiences	Stephen P. Anderson

Table 2. Books released between 1980 and 2011

In order to verify the evolution of the number of publications in recent years, the organization of the books was made for decades, which can be seen in Table 3.

Decade	Number of publications	Percentage
1980-1989	1	2,04%
1990-1999	5	10,20%
2000-2009	29	59,18%
2010-2011	14	28,47%
Total	49	100%

Table 3. Publication of books for decades

The first book found relating the development of products with the emotional factors was *Objects of Desire: Design and Society Since 1750*, by Adrian Forty, published in 1986. The author analyzes some products from 1750 through his appearance affirming that societies use products to express their design values.

In the 1990s, more books about Design and Emotion were released, totaling 5, converging with that Desmet and Hekkert (2009) affirmed about the importance of emotions in the various areas of knowledge in this decade and is also a concern of designers. Thinking about the emotional factors has reflected not only in product development but also in digital interfaces, which became more popular.

Between 2000 and 2009, a significant jump in publications release in the area, the number of books multiplied, reaching 29 works, an average of 2.9 books per year in this decade.

In 2010 and 2011, there are at least 14 published works with four books published in 2010 and ten books until August 2011. In one year and a half already exists in publishing the equivalent of almost half of the publications of the decade of 2000-2009. We can infer that in this pace this decade will surpass the previous one in terms of publications on Design and Emotion.

The number of publications focusing on emotional aspects in product development has increased significantly since the 2000s. Therefore, the release of these books demonstrates the relevance of the subject not only to the scientific community but also for society.

In the next section it will be described how the books were classified to review the publications on the bias of their authors and editors.

AUTHORSHIP

The authorship of books was organized primarily by the number of authors per publication. At least 26 books, almost a half were self-produced involving 1 to 3 authors as shown in Table 4:

Number of authors	Number of publications	Percentage
One author	20	40,81%
Two authors	5	10,20%
Three authors	1	2,04%
Books that are the result of collections of papers	23	46,93%
Total	49	100%

Table 4. Number of authors per publication

Many books are written by a single author, a total of 20 books. Some of these are result of dissertations or thesis as *Designing Emotions* (2002), by Peter Desmet; *A Study on Variable Selection for Kansei Engineering System: Applications for Product Design* (2009), by Chih-Chieh Yang; and *Shoes, cars, and other love stories: Investigating the experience of love for products*, by Beatriz Russo. The academic work when are published in book form may increase the dissemination of knowledge to society.

There is a considerable number of books which are collections of papers organized by editors. This type of publishing books totaled 23 (Table 4) with only three works resulting from the events proceedings (Table 5):

Year	Title of the book	Event
2005	Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction: First International Conference, ACII 2005, Beijing, China, October 22-24, 2005	ACII 2005
2007	Human-computer Interaction: HCI intelligent multimodal interaction environments Part 3	HCI 2007
2009	Affective information processing	ACCI 2005

Table 5. Books resulting from scientific events.

The book *Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction: First International Conference (2005)* and *Affective Information Processing (2009)* have in common as editors, Jianhua Tao and Tan Tien (2005 and 2009), and was a result from the event *Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction (ACCI)* in 2005, the first of the series. Today the ACCI is organized by Humaine Association (2011), created in 2007 with headquarters in Ireland and occurs every two years.

Human-Computer Interaction: HCI intelligent multimodal interaction environments is the result of HCI International 2007 event, which occurred in China and Japan, with many symposia and conferences. This event was attended by 2,300 participants from 76 countries, resulting in the publication of 17 volumes, containing 1,681 articles divided in 10 subjects (HCI International Conference 2007). However for this research, we selected only Part 3 of this volume, since this was a section devoted to the emotions.

It is believed that the number of publications in form of proceedings tends to increase because there are several events being promoted by societies, associations and research centers around the world, given the importance that emotions have assumed for Design.

During the research it was found that the majority of books was published by authors from many places around the world. All the 23 books organized by editors (Table 4) have articles from people from different countries. It was noted during the research

that the editors of these publications has been seeking for a connection with others researches and aren't restricted to your group or research institution. In this sense, they show they are monitoring trends in various locations around the globe.

The information collected in this section shows that the books are well diversified in relation of the authorship and publishing, as regards the number of authors and publishers who collaborate to construct the books, related with the work developed in academy and in the scientific events.

In the next section will describe how the books were analyzed on the bias of its content.

CONTENT

In terms of content, some considerations can be made. Initially, the content focus of the books was classified as product or as a digital interface. With the discovery of more publications, it was necessary to create more classifications. Therefore, the keywords created to identify each the books are:

- Product.
- Digital interface.
- Service.
- Lighting.
- Branding.
- Sound.

These results showed the great potential of application studies in the field of Design and Emotion, not just restricted to products or digital interfaces, but also covering the project of services and brands, lighting and sound environments.

As for the areas of knowledge covered by the books, these were investigated from authors and editors' formal education and areas of interest:

- Administration.
- Architecture.
- Arts.

- Computing.
- Communication.
- Engineering.
- Medicine.
- Psychology.

It's important to say that 73 authors and editors were surveyed, not taking into account the whole universe of authors belonging to the collections of papers. With this data, is possible to see how the area of Design and Emotion is not only multidisciplinary but transdisciplinary as many researchers have a different academic background, allowing a different view of the Design area.

One of the questions that arose during the survey was the inclusion of books about Kansei Engineering or Emotional Engineering, since these publications have appeared on search engines results related to Design and Emotion.

The objective of Kansei Engineering is to transform the mental image of the product desired by the customer into understandable Design characteristics. This methodology was used to develop over 40 products in segment of cars, electronics, cosmetics, clothing, services, computing etc., which demonstrates its importance in product development (Nagamachi and Lokman 2011).

The reason to consider books about Kansei and Emotional Engineering to this research is due to the fact that it was realized that authors/editors had the same objective in the use of emotional factors in product development. In addition, it's possible to identify that many of these authors/editors participate in scientific events in the area of Design and Emotion and some books contain articles related to Kansei and Emotional Engineering, which demonstrate the integration of areas.

In Table 6 is possible to visualize the books about Kansei Engineering and Emotional Engineering found in this study.

Year	Title	Author
2009	A Study on Variable Selection for Kansei Engineering System	Chih-Chieh Yang
2010	Kansei Engineering and Soft Computing: Theory and Practice	Ying Dai, Basabi Chakraborty and Minghui Shi (ed.)
2011	Kansei Engineering: Kansei/Affective Engineering (Industrial Innovation)	Mitsuo Nagamachi (ed.)
2011	Innovations of Kansei Engineering	Mitsuo Nagamachi and Anitawati Mohd Lokman
2011	Emotional Engineering: Service Development	Shuichi Fukuda (ed.)

Table 6. Publications on the Kansei Engineering.

About the Kansei Engineering publications, one conclusion that may be made is the recent consolidation that the knowledge acquired with the releases of books, however, Nagamachi (2011) began to study it in 1970. Yang (2009) noted that in the 90's, studies on Kansei Engineering have spread throughout Asia. In the same decade, in 1998, the Japan Society of Kansei Engineering was created in Tokyo.

Yang's book (2009) is a result of the publication of the doctoral thesis in Industrial Design at National Cheng Kung University, in Taiwan. Given the lack of concern in the selection of variables of Kansei Engineering in product development, the aim of the book is to create methods that work well with ARDS (Affective Response Dimension Selection) and with a PFFS (Product Form Feature Selection).

The publication organized by Ying Dai, Minghui Shi and Basabi Chakraborty is formed mainly by articles from Japanese researchers. The goal is, from different views, showing the fusion of Kansei Engineering and Soft Computing.

In 2011, organized by Mitsuo Nagamachi, *Kansei Engineering: Kansei / Affective Engineering (Industrial Innovation)* has several articles on the Kansei methodology, some in partnership with other researchers elsewhere.

Released the same year of *Kansei Engineering Innovations* was written by Mitsuo Nagamachi with Anitawati Lokman. The goal is to explain the Kansei Engineering, telling its story, case studies, techniques and procedures.

Nagamachi is a professor at Hiroshima University and created more than 40 products using Kansei Engineering. He is also a consultant to several countries including England, Spain, Sweden, Finland, Mexico etc. He received many academic awards, including the Japan Government Prize, in 2008, for developing Kansei Engineering (Nagamachi e Lokman 2011).

Lokman is Doctor of Philosophy in Science (IT) at Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) in Malaysia. She worked in technology companies such as NEC and Toshiba in Japan. And her doctoral dissertation was focused on emotional user experience in Web Design using Kansei Engineering approach (Nagamachi e Lokman 2011).

The last publication found is *Emotional Engineering Service Development*, edited by Shuichi Fukuda. Fukuda is a consulting professor at Stanford University (USA) and visiting professor at the Open University of Japan and Cranfield University (UK). The book presents a wide variety of topics related to Emotional Engineering from contributions of experts. It is an assembly of articles on important aspects of the process of product development: communication, human-computer interaction, transfer of skills, creativity consumer etc. and also shows examples of applications of Emotional Engineering: TV, shoes, displays etc. Most articles are written by authors who belong to educational and research institutions in Japan, but there are also articles by authors from other countries as Taiwan, Korea, the United States, Germany and Italy (Fukuda, 2011).

From the research, it was found that both in Kansei Engineering as the Emotional Engineering studies, there is a predominance of researchers from the Asian continent, where they began to be investigated. But it could be noted that they already have provoked the interest of researchers in other parts of the world.

From the research, it was found that both in the Kansei Engineering as in the Emotional Engineering, there is a predominance of researchers from the Asian continent, where they began to be developed, but note that they already have provoked the interest of researchers in other parts of the world.

Much of the scientific papers were gathered and organized into book form, featuring a variety of topics. In the case of Kansei Engineering and Emotional Engineering, the texts do not have only the concern of how to meet the emotional needs of the user, but also process metrics and applications.

The most words used in the field of study of Design and Emotion recurred the following terms:

- Affect.
- Affective.
- Emotional.
- Cognition.
- Comfort.
- Desire.
- Fun.
- Emotion.
- Emotional.
- Empathy.
- Ergonomics.
- Aesthetics.
- Experience.
- Human factors.
- Humanization.
- Interaction.
- Pleasure.
- Risk.
- Usability.

The use of some of these terms as *experience*, *interaction* and *usability* ultimately increase the scope of the search field in Design and Emotion causing a certain difficulty in defining its studies.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The great interest in the integration of emotional factors in developing products is to satisfy the user in their day-to-day or to entice the consumption. The objective of this study was to analyze what has been published in form of books in this area since 1980 to 2011 to verify the evolution of this knowledge in recent years.

The methodology used to organize data was created using a simple tool, a spreadsheet editor, which turned out to be of vital importance in this study to allow analysis of the content. This type of strategy has allowed the researcher to comprehend and reflect about the publication of these books.

The spreadsheet was being built little by little and often was necessary to redo the data collection because it was necessary to improve the criteria while were found new publications. And this new criteria allowed new thoughts on the matter.

The survey results show an area with high growth in terms of books, resulting in a wider range of knowledge to society, proving the hypothesis of the research.

This research is not finished, because more publications on the subject are released. For further studies, we feel the need to include the systematization of periodicals, dissertations and thesis to complement the research of state of the art Design and Emotion. It is also necessary to collect data on research associations linked to the theme and to the events organized by them.

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